

Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidation of Pinacol by Pyridinium Chlorochromate

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The oxidation of pinacol-(2,3-dimethyl-2,3-butanediol) by pyridinium chlorochromate (pcc) in nitrobenzene-dichloromethane solution have been examined kinetically. The reaction is of first order with respect to [pcc] and [pinacol]. The rate of reaction decreases with increasing proportion of nitrobenzene in solution. The influence of ionic strength could not be carried out because of non aqueous medium. The data show that two molecules of acetone is formed from per molecule of pcc. The reaction is found to be acid-catalysed. The hydride ion transfer mechanism is suggested.

A complex of chromium trioxide, pyridine and hydrochloric acid known as pyridinium chlorochromate¹ (Corey's reagent) oxidises a wide variety of alcohols to carbonyl compounds with high efficiency. One of the fundamental characteristics of oxidation of organic substrates containing hydroxyl groups by pyridinium chlorochromate is the nature of dependence of the reaction rate on pyridinium chlorochromate concentration. The oxidation of diols is of particular interest from mechanistic point of view of the fact that they are easily cleaved under mild conditions. The exact mechanism may not be independent of the chemical nature of oxidiser. The Corey's reagent used for oxidation purpose is slightly acidic in nature and hence proved advantageous in carrying out several cationic cyclisation². The present investigation is a detailed kinetic study of oxidation of pinacol by pyridinium chlorochromate in nitrobenzene-dichloromethane solution. The purpose of investigation is to extend the scope of this extremely efficient and most widely used oxidising agent and to explore and establish mechanistic pathway of reactions involving the oxidative cleavage of diol.

Experimental

All the reagents used of A.R. grade. Solvents were purified in the usual manner³. pcc was prepared by the reported method¹. The reactions were carried out in an electrically operated thermostatic water bath at required temperature ($\pm 0.1^\circ$). The pseudo-first order conditions were maintained and progress of the reaction was followed by estimating the unreacted oxidant iodometrically. The rate constants were evaluated from the plots of \log [oxidant] vs time and reproducible within $\pm 3\%$. The decomposition of pcc is negligible in nitrobenzene-dichloromethane (80 : 20) solution. Hence kinetic investigations were carried out using this range of solvent composition.

Results and Discussion

The pseudo-first order rate constants (Table 1) do not show any appreciable variation with changing initial [pcc] from 4.0×10^{-3} to $1 \times 10^{-2} M$. The first order plot is linear, indicating the first order dependence of rate on [pcc].

TABLE 1—DEPENDENCE OF REACTION RATE ON [PCC]
[Pinacol]=0.05 M, Nitrobenzene : Dichloromethane=
90 : 10 (v/v), Temp.=35°

[PCC] $\times 10^3 M$	k_1 $10^4 s^{-1}$
4.00	9.62
6.00	9.47
8.00	9.35
10.00	9.65

The reactions were studied at different concentration of substrate. It was found that the rate of reaction increases with increasing initial [pinacol]. The plot of $\log k_1$ versus \log [pinacol] is linear (not shown) with unit slope exhibiting first dependence of rate on [pinacol].

It has been observed that increasing percentage of nitrobenzene in the medium decreases the rate, which is in conformity with the observation of Corey and Suggs¹. The plot of $\log k_1$ vs inverse of dielectric constants of medium (not shown) is linear with positive slope which is in agreement with Scatchard expression. This shows that reaction involved the occurrence of an interaction between a dipole and a positive ion⁶.

Attempted acid-catalysed reactions involving dichloro- and trichloroacetic acid were too fast to measure. Organic acids like *p*-toluene sulphonic acid were of little use in view of their meagre solubility in this solvent system. However, Banerjee⁶ reported the use of *p*-toluene sulphonic acid in oxidation of glycollic acid etc by pcc and found

TABLE 2—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS

Temp °C	k_1 $\times 10^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$	Temp. coefficient	E_a kJ mol^{-1}	$\log A$	ΔH^\ddagger kJ mol^{-1}	ΔG^\ddagger kJ mol^{-1}	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ $\text{J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$
25	9.33			6.56	51.83	87.37	119.29
30	12.89	2.04	54.42	6.54	52.21	85.50	119.81
35	19.03	2.10	55.04	6.56	52.17	89.01	119.65
40	26.97			6.56	52.13	89.61	119.76

that the reactions are acid-catalysed. Similar observations were also reported for oxidation of alcohols in chlorobenzene-nitrobenzene mixture in presence of dichloro- and trichloroacetic acid⁷.

Table 2 embraces the thermodynamic parameters.

Stoichiometry and product analysis : To determine the moles of pcc consumed for per mole of pinacol, the concentration of pcc in the reaction mixture was taken 10 times greater than that of pinacol. After completion of reaction the unreacted pcc was estimated iodometrically. It was found that one mole of pcc required one mole of pinacol. The oxidation product of pinacol was acetone which was confirmed by preparation of 2,4-DNP derivative, m.p. 127°.

Mechanism : Free radical mechanism is ruled out since polymerisation of acrylonitrile was not observed. Pinacol is considered to exist mainly as intramolecular hydrogen bonded *gauche* conformation. Both structural and solvent influences noticed leads to the conclusion that the reaction involves the removal of hydride ion, leaving a carbonium ion as a transient intermediate which undergoes further change to form product. However uv spectra (Fig. 1) did not show the existence of intermediate,

Fig. 1 Electronic spectrum of (—) pcc in nitrobenzene-dichloromethane mixture, (---) pinacol in nitrobenzene-dichloromethane mixture and (···) pinacol with pcc in nitrobenzene-dichloromethane mixture.

indicating the unstable nature of intermediate. The process is outlined in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

Cr^{IV} generated in a rate-determining step rapidly reacts with Cr^{VI} .

Cr^{V} , a stronger oxidant, rapidly reacts with the reactive reductance as

A very large increase in rate with acidity suggests the protonation of pcc species, i.e. involvement of Cr^{VI} in rate-determining step and may be the dominant factor. The idea is also supported from the linear plot of $\log k_1$ against $1/D$. Involvement of such species is well-known in chromic acid oxidation⁸.

These data lead to the conclusion that the oxidation of pinacol proceeds via hydride ion transfer mechanism involving formation of a chromate ester which undergoes C—C cleavage to give the product. The observations of earlier workers^{7,9} provide support for this mechanism.

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